

Program Co-Chairs Welcome

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Welcome to Digital Libraries (DL) 2014, the conjoined conference for the ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL) and the International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL). DL 2014 marks the 14th event of JCDL and the 18th in the TPDL series. JCDL and TPDL are premiere international conferences on the broadly interpreted domain of digital libraries that attract researchers, educators, industry leaders, and students working in realm of digital libraries and associated organizational, practical, social, as well as technical issues. DL 2014, hosted by The City University London, brings JCDL and TPDL communities together with its joint program addressing a broad spectrum of topical areas such as user research, system architectures, collection policies, and specialist domains such as digital humanities, preservation, and scholarship.

We have chosen two keynote speakers who amplify the conference's diversity of research topics. The opening keynote will be given by Prof. Dieter Fellner, director of the Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics Research. His talk will address issues of 3D-digitization of our cultural heritage and challenges to make 3D objects first-class citizens of digital libraries. The second keynote will be delivered by Prof. Jane Ohlmeyer from Trinity College in Dublin. She will talk about The 1641 Depositions Project and discuss ground-breaking work in the digital humanities and outline some future challenges in making digital libraries even more powerful tools to analyze complex and often incomplete information.

The Program Chairs, together with the Program Committee and the Organizing Committee, have selected a diverse array of papers, panels, posters and demonstrations consistent with the conference series' long-standing reputation for high quality. This year, we received a total of 233 submissions that each underwent a rigorous review process of first and second level reviewers. The result is a program that reflects the outstanding research being conducted worldwide in the breadth of disciplines that comprise digital libraries. We accepted 31 full paper submissions (29% acceptance rate) and 24 short papers (32% acceptance rate). In addition, there will be two panels: The panel on the first day of the conference will be on the evolving nature of digital libraries towards community-centric platforms and the second one, on the last day of the conference, will be on the use of digital content in library systems. The legendary and always entertaining "minute madness" at the end of the first day of the conference will give authors the opportunity to present 33 accepted posters and 12 demonstrations. The conference will crown a winner of the Vannevar Bush Best Paper Award and a winner of the Best Student Paper Award. Both winners were determined by senior researchers who separately evaluated the quality of all nominees. The awards will be presented at the conference banquet.

DL 2014 continues the tradition of JCDL and TPDL in supporting digital library developers by offering a total of six tutorials that cover a range of timely issues including data mining, reference rot, the Europeana Data Model, preservation of research processes, an introduction to and building digital libraries. The program also includes a record setting eleven workshops that provide a venue for the detailed exploration of the nexus of disciplines. Workshop topics include, amongst others, linking and mining scientific publications, visualizations, preservation policies, and data models. DL 2014 also offers a Doctoral Consortium, as a forum for Ph.D. students worldwide to present their dissertation work in the early stages and receive feedback and advice from a committee of internationally recognized researchers and practitioners. Submissions to the Doctoral Consortium were reviewed by an international Program Committee and students were invited to present at the consortium based on the quality of their proposal and the students' potential to benefit from discussion at the meeting.

The essential ingredient for a top-level conference is high-quality submissions that span over a wide range of digital library topics. The Program Chairs would like to recognize the accomplishment of accepted paper authors and to acknowledge the many others who submitted strong paper proposals. We would further like to thank Program Committee members for mastering the task of reviewing a large number of papers. This conference would not be possible without their dedication and generous contribution of effort.